
The Necessity of Integrating Disaster Nursing and Prolonged Casualty Care Concepts into the Education and Training of Healthcare Professionals in Germany

Introduction: The war in Ukraine in 2022 highlighted the vulnerability of infrastructures and the limits of medical care in crisis zones. Natural disasters such as floods and wildfires, as well as man-made crises like terrorist attacks, regularly demonstrate that civilian healthcare systems can rapidly reach their limits. The COVID-19 pandemic, in particular, exposed global shortages of personnel and materials, underlining the importance of preparedness for prolonged crises and patient care under resource-constrained conditions. These events emphasize the need for a robust and flexible healthcare system capable of functioning under extreme circumstances by preparing staff for patient care in constrained environments. Concepts from military and offshore medicine, as well as from the field of *disaster nursing*, must increasingly inform civilian disaster response and should be incorporated into education, training, and continuing professional development for nurses, physicians, and paramedics.

Nursing Expertise in Disaster Relief and the Necessity of Disaster Nursing: The growing challenges of natural disasters, pandemics, and armed conflicts have underscored the role of nursing and nursing competencies in disaster relief in Germany. In a globalized world shaped by frequent, complex crises, the current training of civilian healthcare professionals requires revision. The relevance of prolonged patient care in civil defense and disaster relief has become apparent in the context of armed conflicts (e.g., Ukraine, Gaza), natural disasters (e.g., the 2021 floods in Germany), and pandemics (e.g., COVID-19). These situations demonstrated that healthcare provision can become severely limited, with everyday resources unavailable and established procedures disrupted. During the COVID-19 pandemic, hospitals faced extreme staffing shortages, requiring the establishment of fever clinics and temporary hospitals, often operated by volunteers from disaster relief organizations (Schenderlein, 2022). Although extreme events are unpredictable, specific crisis competencies can be taught to healthcare professionals to prepare them for disaster conditions. Internationally, specialized nurses—*disaster nurses*—were deployed during the COVID-19 pandemic and in natural disasters, trained at varying levels of expertise (Loke, Li, & Guo, 2021). Such specialization can make a significant difference in disaster response and may also benefit non-nursing professionals. Disaster nursing, as established in the United States and Asia-Pacific regions, focuses on managing extreme crises. While this specialization is not yet widespread in Germany, international guidelines such as those of the International Council of Nurses (ICN) highlight the necessity of expanding disaster nursing training (Lücke, 2024). These competencies include emergency response skills, communication with emergency services, and organizing nursing structures under crisis

conditions. The 2021 Ahr Valley flood in Germany further illustrated these challenges. Evacuations highlighted the difficulties of continuing care for dependent individuals under extreme conditions. Nurses had to improvise when nursing homes were evacuated and residents with complex needs were relocated. Such situations leave no time for consultation of manuals; immediate action is required (Heeser, 2024). Current disaster relief training in Germany largely focuses on short-term emergencies, insufficient for today's realities of asymmetric conflicts and unpredictable extreme weather events (Bundesbereitschaftsleitung des Deutschen Roten Kreuzes, 2020). Healthcare professionals must increasingly be prepared not only for initial treatment but also for extended care of patients in medical shelters or primary facilities under limited personnel, material, and technical resources. At present, few institutions in Germany train staff in disaster nursing or related approaches. Evidence from military medicine and regions accustomed to resource-limited healthcare suggests that structured approaches are critical. The military concept of *Prolonged Casualty Care (PCC)*, developed for situations where evacuation is delayed, is particularly relevant. PCC refers to the extended care of injured or ill patients in resource-limited environments when immediate evacuation is not possible. Its goal is to maximize survival and minimize morbidity through life-saving interventions and supportive care under adverse conditions (Keenan & Riesberg, 2017). Data from military medicine indicate that care times in blocked evacuation chains ranged from 4 to 120 hours (median: 10 hours), with 9.3% of patients dying before transfer to a medical facility (DeSoucy et al., 2017). Mortality rates were higher in such settings than in functioning evacuation systems (Mould-Millman et al., 2022). Core PCC principles include continuous monitoring of vital signs, airway management, bleeding control, circulatory support, infection prevention, wound care, and pain management (Keenan & Riesberg, 2017). Nursing responsibilities become critical when prolonged care is required: preventing infections, maintaining airways, managing fluids and electrolytes, preventing pressure ulcers, ensuring nutrition, and providing psychological support (Ostberg et al., 2018). PCC practitioners must master situational awareness, secure patient and team safety, communicate effectively, improvise with limited equipment, and maintain psychological resilience. Mnemonics such as *HITMAN* and *SHEEP-VOMIT* have been developed as memory aids to support structured decision-making in these contexts. Incorporating PCC into healthcare education could substantially improve preparedness for extended crisis care. Modular training programs are needed to address changing conditions and ensure continuity of care. Nurses in Germany already have access to disaster nursing training through organizations such as the Württemberg Red Cross Nursing Association; however, PCC content is not yet included (DRK-Schwesternschaft Bonn e.V. & Württembergische Schwesternschaft vom Roten Kreuz e.V., 2023). For paramedics and

physicians, integrating basic nursing competencies aligned with PCC principles would be beneficial.

Conclusion: The increasing frequency of global crises demonstrates the urgent need to expand the competencies of healthcare professionals engaged in disaster relief. Current training, focused on short-term emergencies, is insufficient in the face of natural disasters, pandemics, and armed conflicts. Integrating concepts from disaster nursing and military medicine (PCC) into training would ensure extended patient care even under resource constraints and delayed evacuations. A modular, practice-oriented training approach would enhance both technical and psychological resilience, as well as the ability to improvise. Ultimately, adapting disaster relief training across healthcare professions is essential to building a sustainable, resilient healthcare infrastructure capable of maintaining effective patient care under extreme conditions.

References

- Bundesbereitschaftsleitung des Deutschen Roten Kreuzes. (24. 11 2020). *Jugendrotkreuz*. Von Deutsches Rotes Kreuz e.V.:
https://jugendrotkreuz.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Bundesleitungsbriefe_und_Rundschreiben/Mediathek_Rundschreiben_2020/2020-11-24_B__Anlage_1_Rundmail_Curriculum_LLU_Sanitaetsausbildung.pdf
- DeSoucy, E., Shackelford, S. A., DuBose, J. J., Ryan, M. L., Renz, E. M., & Rasmussen, T. E. (2017). Review of prolonged field care knowledge base. *Military Medicine*, 182(3–4), e1684–e1692. <https://doi.org/10.7205/MILMED-D-16-00235>
- DRK-Schwesternschaft Bonn e.V., & Württembergische Schwesternschaft vom Roten Kreuz e.V. (2023, December 29). Basiskurs “Rotkreuzschwestern im Katastropheneinsatz” wird auch 2024 angeboten [Online announcement]. WSSRK Website.
<https://www.wssrk.de/aktuelles/basiskurs-rotkreuzschwestern-2024-katastropheneinsatz/>
- Heeser, A. (2024, September). Fit für den Katastrophenfall. *Die Schwester Der Pfleger*, 12–16.
- Keenan, S., & Riesberg, J. (2017). *Prolonged field care: Beyond the “golden hour”*. Borden Institute, Walter Reed Army Medical Center.
- Loke, A. Y., Li, X., & Guo, C. (2021). The role of nurses in disaster management in the Asia-Pacific region: A literature review. *International Nursing Review*, 68(2), 180–189.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/inr.12602>
- Lücke, S. (2024, September). Katastrophenpflege ist ein Auftrag für die gesamte Berufsgruppe. *Die Schwester Der Pfleger*, 4–10.